

UZBEK FOLK PROVERBS AS A PAREMIOLOGICAL UNIT

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Linguistics: master's degree in English 2nd year

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7676046>

Annotation: This article provides feedback on the scientific features of the research of Uzbek folk proverbs in linguistics as a paremiological unit.

Keywords: proverb, paremiology, folklore, folk art, “ata so’zi” “poslovitsa” “qavlun”.

INTRODUCTION.

The study of Proverbs, sayings and phrases that live as an integral part of the rich spiritual architecture of our people, the display of the life of the people reflected in them, the image of human feelings has always been a matter of relevance. In this regard, our president has such thoughts: “spirituality becomes a powerful force only when he relies on deep knowledge and understanding of the history of his people, its culture.”¹ Comparative study of Uzbek folk Proverbs today is one of the most important issues facing literary studies, linguistics, in particular folklore. It will be possible to open the border between these by studying the genre features of the above, the content and form dependencies between them. If, through this scientific research activity (master's dissertation), we achieve a certain goal, that is, clarify the cross-border relationship between genres, then there will also be a change in the composition of collections in Uzbek folk Proverbs. Based on the revision of the composition of such collections, it is understood that the topic is relevant.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS.

In the literal sense, the study of folk Proverbs, their interest, accumulation began in the XX century. Missionary N. in the collection and publication of Uzbek folk Proverbs. G. Ostroumov's service is great. In 1922, Ghazi scientist Yunusov collected Uzbek folk Proverbs. Later, the word “Uzbek fathers” was published in 1923, which contains 560 articles collected in Khorezm by Mulla Bekjon Rahman ogli. And Sherali Rozzi presented his collection “Uzbek proverbs” in 1926. In addition, a collection of Proverbs was also created under the leadership of Mansur preferably. It included more than 2,500 Proverbs, divided into 34 thematic groups. In contrast to this, in the last edition created by Rajab Jumaniyozov, 1047 proverbs were given on the basis of 22 topics. In the 1984

¹ Karimov. I Uzbekistan national independence economy, politics and ideology. 6 completeness T.: Uzbekistan. 1996, page 80

collection headed by Bahadur Garlishakov, about 4,500 proverbs are presented under 40 topics.

The study of folk Proverbs began together with their publication. In this respect, the heads of words written on the collections of Proverbs at different times, in particular, H. Zaripov, M. Preferred, R. It is necessary to separately indicate the work of Jumaniyozov. In these works, folk proverbs are given a general definition and description, the scope of the topic is determined.²

Genre features of folk Proverbs.

The proverb is one of the genres of folk oral creativity, which has a compact form, but deep content, which arose on the basis of centuries-old life observation of the people, socio-economic, political and cultural experiences. For this reason, Proverbs also acquire a specific educational significance. Because every proverb is tested on the life experiences of people over long years, as well as their living conditions. Russian folklorist V. P. In Anikin's interpretation, "what is not in the experience of the people does not happen in the proverb." And the experience of the people gradually becomes richer for centuries. Proverbs are a necessary tool for our speech in a concise and figurative statement of thought. Therefore also V.G. Belinsky believed that folk proverbs and sayings were "the essence of poetry."

Both in historical sources and among the people, the aphoristic creativity of our people is named by various terms. Proverbs, sayings, sayings, parables, Proverbs, wise words, phrases, sayings, aphorisms, the word of fathers, the word left over from the ancestors, the word abushqa, the word of the mashoyix, the word of the wise, the word of the Ancients, the word of the Ancients, the word of the.¹

The term proverb is derived from the Arabic word qafun – to speak, to say. This genre is present in the oral creativity of all peoples of the world and is common in size, shape, purpose of creation. Even in its naming, closeness is clearly felt. In particular, in the Arabs, "kaflun " - a sentence, a word means, an example is given in the Tajiks terms "zarbulmasal", in the Russian "poslovitsa" - an expression of thought with words, and in the Turkish" ata word " the meaning of remembering the word ancestors is leading. In the work of Mahmud Koshkari "Devoni dictionary Turk", the term "sav" is also presented in the form of remembering the word fathers. Alisher Navoi, on the other hand, used the term "parable" with

² "Uzbek folk Proverbs" I tom Tashkent 1987. Page 11.

an example from a proverb. Well, the term proverb is associated with the concept of “word” in general terms of content. In the oral creativity of all peoples of the world, there is practically no genre as close to each other in form and content as Proverbs. Folklorist scholars call the field of study of Proverbs and sayings paremiology. Paremia is a Greek word with a deep meaning, giving the meaning of a wise word, phrase, proverbs.

Famous European Orientalist scientist, professor G. Wambery returned from his trip to our country in the second half of the 19th century, he wrote: “...the East has long been a land of poetic feelings... therefore, no one should be surprised that the passion for poetry in people living in the fire is stronger than in members of an educated society in Paris or London... in Central Asia, both young – well, everyone-everyone is equally interested in poetic creativity... proverbs can be found both in written language and in living language, heard both in the palace of the land Cossacks and in the fire of the Nomad... the son of the desert listens to such a “word of fathers” all the time with a serious touch on his face. No reasonable statement, no persuasive word, contrary to the meaning of the proverb, can influence his opinion, the innate fanaticism in his nature is manifested in nothing so strongly in anything other than the diligent, harsh belief that the ancestors and the wisdom left by them were wisely told, not wrongly said.”

The genre features of Proverbs are as follows:

- ❖ Proverbs represent a sermon and deep meaning in the content:
- ❖ Folk proverbs are Forman poetic and prose. But prose Proverbs also remind of poetic verses.
- ❖ Proverbs express a strict judgment about a life event-a phenomenon. This judgment is reflected in positive or negative content.
- ❖ The proverb summarizes the private situation in the life of a person from the point of view of the people, the public, life.

The text of the proverb is a generalized statement of personality in linguistics.

The term proverb is found in several Turkic languages: Bashkir, Kazakh, Karakalpak, Kyrgyz, Turkmen, tatar, Uyghur. Tajik also has this term. Tajik folklorist scholars indicate that the term proverb can be an alternative to the Russian term “pogovorka”, and not the Russian meaning “poslovisa” in the Tajik language. The word proverb has the same meaning in Persian as in Tajik. Proverbs were also created with the participation of the proverb. For example:

So'z ko'rki – maqol, er ko'rki – soqol.³

³Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language. II full .-M., 1981, page 135-300

Word blind-proverb, guy blind-beard

This proverb also exists in the tatar language and in the Kazakh language.⁴

The genre of Proverbs of folk oral creativity has the property of being enriched in number and content throughout historical life. That is, proverbs can come out of consumption with the passage of time, and at the same time new and new samples can arise.

The following factors are responsible for the exit of proverbs from consumption:

- Change of historical life As a result of the loss of the need to apply the proverb in social life, the proverb comes to mind from the people
- Proverbs with the participation of historical words disappear over time.
- Some proverbs may also disappear under the influence of the sign of the mouthpiece of oral creativity. A proverb that a generation does not use is doomed to death.

The above reasons lead to the disappearance of the proverb. At the moment, there are no sources of enrichment of the samples of our proverbs either. They consist of:

- ✓ As a result of changes in social life, new Proverbs arise. For example, after the independence of Uzbekistan, the use of the wise word "love for the Motherland is from faith" became popular. Initially, this proverb was used in the book of Abdullah Avlani "Turkic Gulistan or morality" by the Prophet Muhammad (s.a.c) it was said to be Hadithi. But this wise word has not been used much among our people. After independence, it became the most popular proverb.
- ✓ New and new examples of folk Proverbs appeared as a result of the development of economic, social relations between peoples. The proverb "the Apple does not fall far from the agach" is a translation of the "apple horse yabloni daleko ne padaet". Today we are hardly interested in the origin of this proverb.
- ✓ The emergence of new Proverbs will be associated with the words spoken by scholars, wise leaders. In history, when we get acquainted with the work of Joseph Khos Khajib, Ahmad Yugnaki, Alisher Navoi, the author of the so-called aphorism comes across clear wise and wise words. Among them are examples such as, "little by little, he will become wise, and he will gather in layers, and he will become a river".⁵

⁴ Muhammadjon Hakimov, on the terms of Proverbs, Journal of Uzbek language and literature, 1965.

⁵ Safarov Sh. Pragmalinguistics. - Tashkent, 2008

Proverbs are even more remarkable in that they have their own and portable meanings. There are three manifestations of the use of proverbs in the written literature:

- ❖ The folk proverb is exactly quoted.
- ❖ Some words in the proverb change, the meaning is preserved.
- ❖ The poet expresses an idea using the meaning in the proverb.

CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, the role of folk Proverbs has an incomparable place in the spiritual world, maturity and upbringing of children of our people. The paremic genres listed above are from the ancient and mass genres of oral creativity, reflecting the worldview of our people. They reflect in themselves the reality that is taking place in society. Proverbs are characterized by the fact that the word order reflects colorful topics. Folk Proverbs cover every aspect of human life. They reflect both sad days and moments full of joy. We tried to conduct a comparative study of Proverbs at the end of our master's dissertation work.

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